

Women Empowerment and Sustainable Community Development in Kakamega County, Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of the study is to examine the effect of Women Empowerment on Sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya. The specific objectives of the study was to assess the effect of women involvement on Sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya. The study was guided by the empowerment theory and Women empowerment theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population was 3648 respondents comprising of Chairpersons of all the respective registered women groups in Kakamega County. The sample size was 36 respondents through Yemen formulae. Data collection instrument will be structured questionnaires. A structured questionnaire used to collect the primary data collection instrument. Piloting will be done to test both the reliability and validity of the research instrument. Content validity will be used to measure the validity of the instrument. It relied on the knowledge of the experts who are familiar with the subject matter being measured. Cronbach's alpha used to measure the reliability of the questionnaire by providing the internal consistency during a pilot study done to 36 registered women groups in Bungoma County. The regression model used to analyse the data obtained to investigate the relationship between the variables. Based on the findings, the study concluded that women involvement has a significant effect on sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya ($\beta_1=0.372$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.000 was less than the significant level of 0.05. The study came up with the following recommendations; the community should not hold women back from contributing to important economic activities in the society by not allowing discrimination and inequality is an integral part of the socio-economic project of transformation. They should encourage women involvement and participation to dialogue and collaboration with community members since wide and active participation from community members will result in a good decision made in the development programme and that the more community members are involved, the more people will get empowered for best strategy of ensuring improved community and better livelihoods for global citizens and maximum social benefits to communities. The study is significant to various stakeholders involved with Sustainable community development and to the researcher as well.

Keywords: Women involvement, Sustainable Community Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Communities can be defined by characteristics that the members share, such as culture, language, tradition, law, geography, class, and race. As Shaeffery (2012) argues, some communities are homogeneous while others are heterogeneous; and some united while others conflictive. Zanty (2021) points out three aspects of communities, namely:

community is a group structure, whether formally or informally organized, in which members play roles which are integrated around goals associated with the problems from collective occupation and utilization of habitation space; members of the community have some degree of collective identification with the occupied space, and the community has a degree of local autonomy and responsibility.

The relationship between community empowerment and human development has been a significant concern, especially community empowerment and development issues Phan (2013). The United Nations claims that empowering women is beneficial for community parse and the socio-economic development for all. A country needs to invest more in community capabilities and empower them to contribute to humans' development in general (Nussbaum, 1995). In the 1990s, development programs started to recognize the role of women's empowerment in human development. The United Nations first defined women empowerment after the 4th World Conference on Women in Beijing in 1995. During the conference, five components of community empowerment were identified as women's sense of self-worth, right and ability to determine choices, right to have access to opportunities and resource, right to control their own lives, and right or ability to influence the direction of social change to create more just social and economic order (United Nations, 1995). According to World Bank (2014), as the world moved to conclusion of the Millennium development Goals that were access their achievements by 2015, the world development strategists found it that in countries where the communities were actively involved in development projects implementation, the millennium development goals had been achieved to greater percentage as compared to countries where passive participation was employed in development projects implementation (Gupta, P. 2020). Participation in development projects implementation across the globe has gained popularity as the sure way of ensuring that development projects success and sustainability is achieved (UN, 2017).

UN (2017) has also indicated that involving all the community members in development projects design, plans, resources mobilization and prioritization influences the rates at which economic development is achieved since the development projects implemented in countries are directly tied to community needs and perceptions. However, despite the fact that studies in developed countries like the USA, China, Europe and Parts of Russia. (Endalcatchew, 2016) have shown that women empowerment has been accepted and women are involved actively in development projects implementation, a number of countries in the developing continents like parts of Asia, Africa and south America have shown that women are left out due to a number of reasons. In Philippines for example, the participation of women in Sustainable community development projects implementation in Manila has been and is still pegged at 32% for over 15 years now (UNDP, 2015). A number of factors for poor participation of women in Sustainable community development projects implementation have been listed to include: poor gender roles and classifications, poor levels of income of the women, poor cultural and traditional subscriptions that deny women rights to own properties, poor levels of education, poor religious subscriptions and classifications that discriminate women over some opportunities in the community among other factors not listed (Gupta, P. 2020). Although a close study by the UN Women (2017) has shown that women who have been involved in Sustainable community development in the capital city (manila) have been posting impressive results in various perspectives; a need for empowering women in the community. For example, much of the home-based poverty mitigation projects are implemented by women, the decisions on which type of project can be implemented or the models to be used are done by women and the results are better by 30% as compared to cases where men perform these duties (Bui, et.al., 2021).

Sustainable community development is a socio-spatially embedded activity, and the masculinities that are given a normative role in Sustainable community development policies are a manifestation of the social construction of gender, time, geography, economy, and culture (Harrison et al. 2020). Ojediran and Anderson (2020) indicated that empowering women should take into account the social context in which communities occurs since it is socially integrated and could be seen as a social activity with economic effects. Haugh and Talwar (2016) investigated how social communities, women's empowerment, and social transformation are related. The social order itself has changed thanks to creative business practices that have supported women's economic activities. Osei and Zhuang (2020) studied empowering women through female activities, which has implications for performance and social innovation, and relational social capital. Sharma and Kumar (2021) attributed women's empowerment to social activities, which fared better than non-governmental organizations despite having the same ability to promote women's empowerment (Hibbs et al., 2022). Khanna (2019) argued that women should be empowered and supported through social activities in their development, according to research on the method in which women in the business sector have taken the initiative to challenge women

in rural regions to prove themselves. This is consistent with Venugopalan et al. (2021), who asserted that women in India could be empowered through capacity-building and social inclusion programs. Argyrou and Charitakis (2018) introduced female involvement in social activity initiatives, which may result in job opportunities that help remove current barriers and successfully ensure that women's right to work is realized. Kumari (2020) and Zhou and Johnston (2020) used social media to empower women and encourage women Sustainable community development since it has become a powerful platform for the discussion of women's rights and to encourage the government and policymakers to step up commitments and formulate policies for gender equality. Social media has empowered women manifold both socially, psychologically, and financially in community (Ibarra, Diana, and Natalia Stengel. 2021). Kelly's (2020) women empowerment is the route to Sustainable community development. Sevig (2015) suggests that, women's situation can be improved by strengthening their participation in developmental decision-making processes at all levels, encouraging their participation in elections and government, favoring their active participation in local communities and civil society organizations as well as in national political life, adopting targeted policies and instruments, providing them with the necessary tools, notably in the form of guidance and protection models, and addressing their problems and concerns in the political process through the creation of the parliamentary groups on the status of women.

Studies have shown that despite that women empowerment is directly proportional to Sustainable community development and their performances, very little being done about women empowerment in the society (Chagaka and Rutatora 2016). In Kenya, according to USAID (2018), empowering women to participate fully in economic life across all sectors is essential to build the economies, achieve international agreed goals for development and sustainability, and improve quality of life for women, men, family and communities as a whole. Women are very much disadvantaged in all spheres. For example, women are not allowed to own property like land, women never inherit their parents' properties as compared to men, women have not been given chances to sit in major community development committee and never make major decisions (Laboso, 2014). African Development Bank (2017) has indicated it worse that in instances where women are allowed to sit in development seating, their ideas are normally brushed off and sometimes they are reminded on their roles in cooking and serving the men in these special gatherings. Women have not been given a chance in Africa as compared to men despite the fact that they contribute much than the men in terms of community resources mobilization, community labor providence etc (UN Women, 2016). However, in countries like South Africa and Liberia where women have been given some special recognition through various women empowerment programmes, their efforts in Sustainable community development are eminent (Murunga, 2017). In Soweto, during the transformation of the slum into a modern peri-urban settlement, women were credited for their roles in: providing cheap labour, solving conflicts on resettlement among various communities, proving of other production materials like land (those who owned land), providing the government with the best housing models that addressed the needs of the city slum dwellers and others (UN, Women, 2017).

Sustainable community development and related concepts such as community engagement, capacity building, community control and participation are all strategies of empowerment (Campbell et al., 2007). These concepts are critical elements to promote health and well-being in ways that are relevant, meaningful and sustainable for the intended beneficiaries. Sustainable community development is a process of organising or supporting community groups in identifying their priority health issues, planning and acting upon their strategies for social action and change, thereby gaining increased self-reliance and decision-making power as a result of their experiences (Labonte, 1993). Sustainable community development is within the 'organizational' or 'community' dimension of the Wallenstein's multi-dimensional empowerment framework. Empowerment is defined as a process whereby individuals and groups of people become stronger and more confident in controlling or exerting influence over the issues affecting their lives. This involves the ability of people to assert and claim their legitimate rights in any given situation and their capacity to accept and willingly discharge responsibilities towards oneself, others and society. It entails special responsibility of a wider society to consciously work towards creating social environments and relationships that bring the best out of people. Following the work of a number of Sustainable community development practitioners including Wallerstein (1992) and Tsey & Every (2000), empowerment is viewed as an ecological or multi-level construct involving three distinct but closely related dimensions: personal or psychosocial empowerment; organizational or group empowerment and community or structural empowerment. Sustainable community development and empowerment sometime have been used too loosely by different people to mean different things over the years. A recent review by Campbell et al. (2007) found 'a great deal of confusion and contention in the literature about the term 'Sustainable community development' and its constituent concepts of

'community', 'participation', 'involvement', 'power', 'capacity' and 'empowerment'. There is also skepticism as to the value and efficacy of Sustainable community development and empowerment in promoting health. The practitioner needs to address and clarify four important issues prior to using the Sustainable community development and empowerment.

It is worth noting that the Kakamega County government appreciates that there is need to work on empowering the women as a way of increasing their capabilities. One of the ways that this will be achieved is by providing institutions that will attend the women training and their skill development. Vocational training institutions will also need to be expanded. The empowerment of women by giving them the skills that they learn through trainings and experiences to be done hand in hand with creation of opportunity and provision of the financial and material resources that would be needed for the skills to be fully utilized. This introduces the need of women inclusive empowerment programs for them and by the women themselves.

According to Murunga (2017), in Kenya there is a challenge of women empowerment and their role in Sustainable community development. According to him in Kenya, women are greatly discriminated, undermined and never put on spheres of development. He for example cited the post-election 2008 where women and children suffered most. The areas where women suffered more included Nyanza, rift valley, coast and many more. However during reconciliation time there were two women who sat on the big bench and their views were from time to time opposed by men who overpowered them. Besides women do not have access to properties, securities for development loan and do not inherit land and other properties, they do not have equal access to education and vocational skills. Women are treated differently from men their ability to participate and involved in development projects is compromised leading to poor results (Arthur 2017).

Few women in Africa hold decision-making positions. None-representation of women in any organization implies that policies facing them are not adequately addressed. There is also overwhelming evidence that development policies and projects were formulated without the involvement of rural women in most African countries (Hunger Project, 2000). The majority of population in developing countries lives in rural areas, where they play the role of food producers. Development is not an isolated activity and it implies progress from a lower state to a preferred higher one (Olopoenia, 1983; Pradip, 1984). In Kenya women's position does not differ from the above situation. It is not uncommon to find women supporting very large families although the majority of them are still very poor. Therefore Sustainable community development projects which are usually formed with the aim of improving the living conditions of the poor cannot be effective unless women participate in their projects' formulation, design and implementation and evaluation as contributors as well as beneficiaries. In this area women are the main providers of basic services such as housing, education for their children, clothing and food. Although women do all these, their role remains largely unrecognized. Women are considered to be the drivers of economies in many societies especially in the rural areas. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the effect of women involvement on community in Kakamega County, Kenya

2. WOMEN INVOLVEMENT ON SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

Myers (2015) observes that, worldwide, women perform two-thirds of the world's work, earn one-tenth of the world's income, are two thirds of the world's illiterate, and owns less than one hundredth of the world's property. This shows that women stand from a disadvantaged position where traditional perception about their roles restricts their contributions and participation in such development projects. This perception tends to hold women back from contributing to important economic activities in the society (USAID, 2016). In many African countries e.g. women in South Africa's rural areas manage their families while their husbands work in the cities, industries or mines. Traditionally, women have been regarded as a lot who belong at home where they are expected to minister to the needs of their husband and children, but decisions on economic and political issues are solely undertaken by men (Zondo, 1995). Addressing the negative effects of gender discrimination and inequality is an integral part of the socio-economic project of transformation (Kruppenbach, 1987), observes that despite the equality provisions in many African constitutions and land restitution process established since 1994, it has become highly unlikely that women will be in a position to make claims as individuals (Friedman, 1999).

Community involvement is thus the process of engaging in dialogue and collaboration with community members but with varying application and definition, depending on the context in which it occurs. For some, it is a matter of principle; for others, practice; for still others, an end in itself (World Bank, 2015). Community participation can also be regarded as a means to educate citizens and to increase their competence (Bragia, et al., 2016); a vehicle for influencing decisions that

affect the lives of citizens and an avenue for transferring political power. Armutage (2019) defined citizen involvement as a process by which citizen's act in response to public concerns, voice their opinions about decisions that affect them, and take responsibility for changes to their community. Yet still, Westergare (2018) defined involvement as collective effort to increase and exercise control over resources and institutions on the part of groups and movements of those up till then excluded from control.

Rural women's involvement in development has been the focus of intensive debates at most international forums in the past years. Among those forums that recognized the plight of the Third World women's involvement in development process are the 1995 Nairobi Forward Looking Strategies for advancement of women, the 1995 Beijing Declaration and the United Nations Development Fund for Women. These forums expressed that each member state was expected to promote women's economic independence, including the creation of employment, access to resources and credit, the eradication of the persistent and increasing burdens of poverty, malnutrition, poor health and illiteracy (Allen & Thomas 1992). Although such declarations increased an awareness and understanding of the problems facing rural women and their needs, it has not yet resulted in significant development priorities in terms of their expectations and aspirations. Women's involvement in development dates for long time as suggested by the literature, however, this involvement has not been recognised by other people, especially men (UNIFEM 2000).

The impact of development on rural women differs from that of women in urban areas. Substantial evidence suggests that rural women have been consistently neglected in this process (Meer 1998). There is also overwhelming evidence that development policies and projects were formulated without the involvement of rural women in most African countries (Hunger Project 2000). The majority of population in developing countries lives in rural areas, where they play the role of food producers. Women in rural areas can also contribute to development in the same manner as those in urban areas, if they are initiated and guided in the development processes of their choice (Cartledgy 2017).

The women in contemporary society are contextualized on the periphery of mainstream policy process that disadvantages them. There are various conceptualizations of the women. According to Kurth-Schai (1988) they can be mapped along a women-in-society continuum. As expressions of participation, women are organizing groups for social and political action, planning programs of their own choosing, and advocating their interests in the community. They are raising consciousness, educating others on matters that concern them, and providing services of their own choosing. No single strategy characterizes all approaches to participation. Activities like these can be conceptualized in various ways. For example, Roger Hart (1997) identifies activities and places them on the rungs of a vertical "ladder of participation" in accordance with the power they exercise; Danny HoSang (2003) analyzes women organizing, women development, and other models on a horizontal continuum; and David Driskell (2002) describes several "steps in the process" from gathering information to program evaluation. Currently women in Kakamega County are involved in different activities meant to improve their livelihoods. There are development projects harnessed both by the government and non-governmental organizations. However, these projects have been marred with misappropriation of funds and lack of proper planning. Kenya Women Employment Opportunities by World Bank has enabled and promoted women empowerment in Kakamega County. This happens when women of different backgrounds are trained on various projects and entrepreneurial skills. After training, funds are allocated to them to start their own projects or businesses. There has been improvement of the lives of women as a result of such projects. But on the hand sustainability of these projects have been compromised due to misappropriation of resources, misplaced priorities, and changing environments; social, economic and political.

Several studies have been done on women empowerment and Sustainable community development. In relation to female entrepreneurship in KSA, Alkhaled (2021) explored women's entrepreneurship as a political reform of feminism for social change in Saudi Arabia. The results demonstrated the entrepreneurs wanted to empower women within their firm to cultivate a feminist consciousness within their entrepreneurial network. Alshmary et al. (2021) studied the attitudes of Saudi women toward empowering them in the online labor market and the impact of the social and economic characteristics on it. Al-Qahtani et al. (2021) designed and validated a tool for women's emancipation among Saudi women employed as academic and administrative employees. Parveen (2022) indicated that the Saudi government had developed various laws and reforms to empower women in the workplace, including gender equality, which resulted in a new paradigm shift for Saudi women entering the labor sector. In an effort to realize Saudi Arabia's "Vision 2030", it has examined the effectiveness of government initiatives to empower women (Rizvi and Hussain 2022). Alessa et al. (2022)

evaluated the Saudi context, the difficulties, and the suggested course of action in light of the Saudi Vision 2030, and the economic empowerment of women in Saudi Arabia was found to contribute to the achievement. Rusell and Campen (2011) in their study on the factors and inclusion in women development: What we can learn from marginalized women, concluded that by considering dominant culture though as a collection of peculiar norms and habits, it was evident that marginalization/exclusion of women was majorly through institutions and programs that promote women marginalization from community initiatives and development in society. This study however, dealt with the women in the United States, a population which was far away from the scope of this study and with totally different characteristics. Kimakwa (2018) on his part researched on the Influence of Catholic Church funded projects on socio-economic development of women in Kakamega County and concluded that the Catholic church, in its funded projects had enable majority of the women in Kakamega County to access necessary health, social and other services as well as have an awareness of how they can keep away from unnecessary conflicts and co-exist peacefully. However, much as the study was within the same area of coverage, it concentrated on the Catholic Church which limited its scope.

Mwei (2018) in his study on factors influencing women participation in the implementation of Sustainable community development projects in Konoin Sub-County of Bomet County, concluded that women involvement in the women projects influenced women participation in Sustainable community development projects but they were not involved in the appointment of evaluation committee. This study was carried out in only one county which was again away from the scope of this study. The population also comprised different cultural beliefs and practices from those practiced in Kakamega County. As much as many studies have done in Sustainable community development area, not much has been done on women empowerment in communities for example, on matters to do with education in sub counties, many areas majority hold up to secondary education and few rations attain up to college levels. This leaves them with a challenge to fully participate for the achievement of social or economic ends, to specify how resources are allocated. Tasks, responsibilities and value are assigned as well as determining who gets what, who does what, and who decides. Therefore men having a better hand in education dominate most of the social institutions and women in most cases become passive recipients of male chauvinism. Although women may be interested in participating in Sustainable community development projects, the outcome of such projects does not seem to benefit them economically as they are rarely involved in decision making (Vixathep, 2011). Their participation is sometimes hampered by the obstacles placed on their way by the society (Ogbuji, 2015). These barriers of gaps may include inadequate education, cultural, economic factors. This implies that their participation in such development entities can be described as disjointed and unsatisfactory.

3. METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for the study was 3648 registered women groups comprising; Chairpersons of all the respective registered women groups in Kakamega County. The sample size for registered women group beneficiaries was 360. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The data was reduced, organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analyzed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. Once data is collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was coded, entered and analyzed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The first specific objective of the study was to assess the effect of women involvement on community in Kakamega County, Kenya. The respondents were requested to indicate their level of agreement on statements relating to the effect of women involvement on community in Kakamega County, Kenya. A 5 point Likert scale was used where 1 symbolized strongly disagree, 2 symbolized disagree, 3 symbolized neutral, 4 symbolized agree and 5 symbolized strongly agree. The results were as presented in Table 4.1. From the results, the respondents agreed that Community perception tends to hold women back from contributing to important economic activities in the society. This is supported by a mean of 3.921 (std. dv = 0.970). In addition, as shown by a mean of 3.855 (std. dv = 0.841), the respondents agreed that Gender discrimination and inequality is an integral part of the socio-economic project of transformation. Further, the respondents agreed that Community involvement is thus the process of engaging in dialogue and collaboration with community members but with varying application and definition, depending on the context in which it occurs. This is shown by a mean of 3.731 (std. dv = 0.914).

The respondents also agreed that women involvement promotes women's economic independence, including the creation of employment, access to resources and credit, the eradication of the persistent and increasing burdens of poverty, malnutrition, poor health and illiteracy. This is shown by a mean of 3.678 (std. dv = 0.869). With a mean of 3.689 (std. dv = 0.856), the respondents agreed that Women in rural areas can also contribute to development in the same manner as those in urban areas, if they are initiated and guided in the development processes of their choice. Lastly, the respondents agreed that Women involvement is a panacea to building community capacity and strengthen social development. This is shown by a mean of 3.626 (std. dv = 0.788).

Table 4.1: Effect of Women Involvement on Community in Kakamega County, Kenya

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Community perception tends to hold women back from contributing to important economic activities in the society	3.921	0.970
Gender discrimination and inequality is an integral part of the socio-economic project of transformation	3.855	0.841
Community involvement is thus the process of engaging in dialogue and collaboration with community members but with varying application and definition, depending on the context in which it occurs	3.720	0.926
Promote women's economic independence, including the creation of employment, access to resources and credit, the eradication of the persistent and increasing burdens of poverty, malnutrition, poor health and illiteracy	3.685	0.958
Women in rural areas can also contribute to development in the same manner as those in urban areas, if they are initiated and guided in the development processes of their choice	3.678	0.867
Women involvement is a panacea to building community capacity and strengthen social development	3.626	0.788
Aggregate	3.788	0.873

4.1 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics in the current study focused on correlation and regression analysis. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength of the relationship while regression analysis was used to determine the relationship between dependent variable Sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya) and independent variables (women involvement,).

4.1.1 Correlation Analysis

The present study used Pearson correlation analysis to determine the strength of association between independent variables (women involvement) and the dependent variable (Sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya) dependent variable. Pearson correlation coefficient range between zero and one, where by the strength of association increase with increase in the value of the correlation coefficients. The current study employed Taylor (2018) correlation coefficient ratings where by 0.80 to 1.00 depicts a very strong relationship, 0.60 to 0.79 depicts strong, 0.40 to 0.59 depicts moderate, 0.20 to 0.39 depicts weak.

Table 4.2: Correlation Coefficients

		Sustainable community development Women involvement	
Sustainable community development	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	340	
Women involvement	Pearson Correlation	.839**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	340	340

From the results on table 4.2 above, there was a very strong relationship between women involvement and community in Kakamega County, Kenya ($r = 0.839$, p value = 0.002). The relationship was significant since the p value 0.002 was less than 0.05 (significant level).

4.1.2 Regression Analysis

Multivariate regression analysis was used to assess the relationship between independent variables (women involvement) and the dependent variable (Sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya)

Table 4.3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.982	.844	.849	.12320

a. Predictors: (Constant), women involvement,

The model summary on table 4.3 above was used to explain the variation in the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The r -squared for the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.844. This implied that 84.4% of the variation in the dependent variable (Sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya) could be explained by independent variables (women involvement).

Table 4.4: Analysis of Variance

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	15.024	1	3.019	73.32	.000 ^b
1 Residual	6.762	339	.033		
Total	21.786	340			

A. Dependent Variable: Sustainable Community Development in Kakamega County, Kenya

B. Predictors: (Constant), Women Involvement

From table 4.4. above, the ANOVA was used to determine whether the model was a good fit for the data. F calculated was 73.32 while the F critical was 2.112. The p value was 0.000. Since the F -calculated was greater than the F -critical and the p value 0.000 was less than 0.05, the model was considered as a good fit for the data. Therefore, the model can be used to predict the effect of women involvement on sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya.

Table 4.5: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.213	0.049		5.496	0.000
	Women Involvement	0.372	0.098	0.366	3.727	0.000

a Dependent Variable: sustainable community development

The regression model was as follows:

$$Y = 0.213 + 0.372X_1 + \varepsilon$$

According to the results, women involvement has a significant effect on sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya ($\beta_1=0.372$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.000 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study concluded that women involvement has a significant effect on sustainable community development in Kakamega County, Kenya ($\beta_1=0.372$, p value= 0.000). The relationship was considered significant since the p value 0.000 was less than the significant level of 0.05.

The study came up with the following recommendations; the community should not hold women back from contributing to important economic activities in the society by not allowing discrimination and inequality is an integral part of the socio-economic project of transformation.

They should encourage women involvement and participation to dialogue and collaboration with community members since wide and active participation from community members will result in a good decision made in the development programme and that the more community members are involved, the more people will get empowered for best strategy of ensuring improved community and better livelihoods for global citizens and maximum social benefits to communities.

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